

Investigating SDBD Plasma Treatment for Bacterial Inactivation and Biofilm Removal on Polymeric Surfaces

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This study investigates the efficiency of a novel plasma technology, utilizing a water-based surface dielectric barrier discharge (SDBD), for the inactivation of planktonic and sessile *E. coli* bacteria. This technique leverages the unique properties of SDBD generated at the interface of a liquid electrode, ambient air, and a dielectric tube, to uniformly treat internal polymeric surfaces relevant to medical tubes and devices.

The new design of the water-based SDBD, with the liquid acting as an electrode, allows for the generation of reactive species in close proximity to the target surface¹. This creates a higher efficiency in the inactivation of bacteria and biofilm removal. The controlled movement of the plasma ring along the tube's inner wall ensures uniform treatment, which is crucial for applications involving complex geometries, such as catheters. Also, the use of atmospheric pressure operation facilitates the experiment setup and decreases the cost of the process.

We examined the antimicrobial properties of the plasma on two different sets of conditions: (1) direct treatment of planktonic *E. coli* (CCM 3954) in water solution, varying the power input and treatment time, and (2) destruction of 48-hour *E. coli* biofilms grown inside the inner surface of polymeric tubes. For the latter, a moving plasma ring was employed to simulate catheter treatment, examining the influence of power and plasma ring moving speed. The SDBD discharge was operated at atmospheric pressure with a 10-20 kV, ~31 kHz sinusoidal high-voltage waveform. Bacterial reduction was quantified using standard microbiological plate-counting techniques, while cytometry assays determined the percentage of dead cells.

Varying the power input, treatment time, and ring speed allowed for the optimization of SDBD plasma treatment parameters. The observed relationship between these parameters and the bacterial reduction efficiency allows for the development of tailored treatment protocols for specific applications.

Our results demonstrate up to 6 log reduction for planktonic cells, indicating a significant decrease in bacterial population within the liquid medium, with complete biofilm destruction achievable, depending on plasma parameters.

This research highlights the future application of water-based SDBD for enhanced surface sterilization and treatment of materials, particularly for medical applications involving inner surface decontamination.

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References

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